

**XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION
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**FROM SCREEN TO SCHOLAR: THE ROLE OF MEDIA IN STUDENT
EDUCATION**

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Abstract: *The article examines the dual impact of media on students in the digital age. It discusses the negative aspects, such as distractions from social media and the potential decline in critical thinking skills due to passive information consumption. It illustrates these points with examples like Instagram, where students can easily lose track of time. Conversely, the article highlights the positive benefits of media, including enhanced learning opportunities through educational content on platforms like Instagram and the use of AI tools like ChatGPT, Kahoot, which can support students' studies when used appropriately.*

Key words: *Students, media, people, technology, videos, information, Instagram, negative, learn, studying, questions, answers, languages, encourage.*

Introduction:

In today's society, we are all bombarded with the latest technology. Every single data and information can tell us what is happening in our world; what can we do to tackle some problems, how can we make our small business, what kind of websites people should use to get tickets to foreign countries. I can say that, the digitalized century, that we are living, is helping us at the same time. In the field of education, medicine, business, science and even universe, people are accustomed to rely on technology. So, let us explore together the importance of media, which is part of technology, for students both negatively and positively.

Main body:

As we know, media is not always helpful. The videos and contents, which students come across in daily life, lead to waste most of their time. Especially social media and entertainment platforms can be highly distracting. Students may find it difficult to concentrate on their studies when they have constant access to notifications and engaging content. For instance, let us take an Instagram as an example of this argument. You take your phone for at least 15 minutes in order to have a little rest. You watch one video that interests you and the more you scroll, the more interesting videos will appear. Consequently, you will not notice how you lost your 3 hours. Moreover, relying heavily on media for information can hinder the

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development of critical thinking skills. Students may become tend to consuming information passively rather than analyzing it. Additionally, over reliance on media can result the weakness of group working, engaging in traditional activities, reading books and participating games. However, there is the other side of the coin also, using media has many advantages for students. To begin with, with the help of media students can significantly increase their level of knowledge and study. As a support of this idea, again we can talk about an Instagram. There are many bloggers, who are developing their business by teaching people different well-known languages, explaining to students how to make presentations, handouts and study materials. For example, a Russian girl Lingua Marina. She has an account on Instagram, which she uses for teaching English to people all around the world. With the assistance of her videos, contents, reels and the life about in America students will be motivated to study better. Another useful media tool for students is ChatGPT. It is the most popular AI app among students all over the world. It makes the life of all students easier. They can find answers to all the difficult questions that bother them. Many people think that, the negative sides of this artificial intelligence are greater; it stops students to do their tasks on their own, they may become overly dependent on ChatGPT for answers, which can hinder their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. However, it is important for them to use ChatGPT as a supplementary tool rather than a primary source of learning. Because, they engage in their studies actively and critically, learn to think outside of the box and broaden their horizons. Apart from that, there are a boatload of telegram channels, websites and programs to encourage students studying. These tools provide students with materials, tests and exercises that appeared in real exams. By reviewing this information, they can pass their exams easily. In addition, there is a website called “Kahoot”, an online competition, which teachers make questions for students, so that they will be able to find answers to every question. The funniest part of this website is that, students can choose the photos of animated animals with amazing accessories (caps, glassed, jewelry, etc.) After solving all tests, the website determines winners, this competitive aspect, encourages students to participate actively. Because, “Kahoot” makes learning enjoyable through gamification.

Research methodology:

1) The impact of social media on education is an increasingly relevant topic as more and more students are using social media in schools and their everyday lives. While there is no denying the potential benefits of social media usage in education,

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such as enhancing communication and collaboration among students, there is also the potential for negative effects, such as distractions from classwork and cyberbullying. Keep on reading to learn more about social media and student improvement. (Schoolcues block)

2) Learning media are tools and materials used by teachers to facilitate and support the process of learning activities in the classroom. The purpose of learning media is to increase student involvement in the learning process. Interesting and varied learning media can increase student participation in the learning process. Using learning media can also increase understanding of the lessons being taught (Berpusi publishing journal).

3) According to “Carleton College Journal” media can be used in almost any discipline to enhance learning, both in class and for out-of-class assignments. Short film and television clips, written articles, and blog posting can be viewed to reinforce concepts and spark discussion. Songs and music videos, especially when the lyrics are available, can be used to same content.

4) Other research suggests that people learn abstract, new and novel concepts more easily when they are presented in both verbal and visual form. (Salomon, 1979).

5) Other empirical research shows that visual media make concepts more accessible to students than text media and help with later recall. (Cowen, 1984).

6) In Willingham’s research (2009) he asks a simple question to make his point “Why do students remember everything that is on television and forget what in lecture?” Because visual media helps students retain concepts and ideas. (Bransford, Browning, and Cocking)

Conclusion:

In conclusion, I can say that, media can enhance students' learning and boost their grades, but it can also negatively influence their minds and lead to time wasting simultaneously. Therefore, it is better to use it wisely in the right way. It is important for students, teachers, and parents to find a good balance when it comes to using media. This means setting limits on the screen time, encouraging active participation with educational content, and teaching students how to identify trustworthy sources of information. By using media wisely, students can enjoy its benefits while reducing its negative effects. The aim should be to create a learning environment where media helps education instead of distracting from it.

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1. Bransford, Browning, and Cocking

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2. Berpusi Journal
3. Carleton College Journal
4. Cowen, 1984
5. Salomon, 1979
6. Schoolcues block
7. Willingham's research (2009)